

Ordinary Monstrosity: The World of Goosebumps

by Perry Nodelman

When R. L. Stine's Goosebumps books first appeared, only a few years ago, many parents, teachers, and librarians viewed the mere existence of the new series as a monstrous intrusion into the well-intentioned world of children's publishing, and the content of the novels themselves as an equally monstrous intrusion into the ordinarily innocent minds of young readers. But as time has passed and the series has continued to be phenomenally popular with young readers, it becomes harder and harder to find adults willing to be more than mildly distressed by Goosebumps. When asked about children's apparently insatiable enthusiasm for these books, most adults I've spoken to lately tend to say something along the lines of, "Well, at least they're reading *something*."¹

Comments of this sort clearly express dismay about children's enthusiasm for writing that strikes many adults as being not only unchildlike but also without merit—in a word, trashy. But the comments also acknowledge the undeniable presence of the books as an important and unavoidable part of children's literature, not so much an aberration as a somewhat off-putting aspect of the normally expectable, like traffic jams or tight shoes or a bad cold. The ordinary has expanded to include this one particular form of the monstrous.

Intriguingly, this change in adult attitudes replicates what happens in the novels themselves. In each of the Goosebumps books, something or someone monstrous and impossible intrudes into an otherwise ordinary world. Its presence causes fear and distress for the twelve-year-old child or children who must deal with it. But, by the end of the story, normalcy reasserts its primacy. Somehow or other—as I'll show later, it happens in a variety of ways—the boringly ordinary world manages to absorb the impossible and to continue on in its boringly ordinary way. What at first seemed like a serious aberration from logic and order has come to be acknowledged, expected. It's upsetting, perhaps, but nothing to be especially concerned or alarmed about.

Nor is it only the plots of the novels that replicate this pattern. There are a variety of ways in which the Goosebumps books invite their young readers to confront that which is usually identified as frighteningly monstrous and horrifically abnormal and to accept it as normal, not just in the world the novels describe but in their own lives and characters.

Marketing: The Invitation to Monstrosity

Before Goosebumps appeared, there was little that might be identified as horror fiction for young readers. Within a short time, the books in this series absorbed so much of the market that they might well be described as the books young children

most often read or bought.² Once more, the monstrous became merely ordinary. The success of the series represents a merchandising triumph. How does it work?

To begin with, the publishers of Goosebumps reuse successful ploys developed by marketers of popular series for children over the past century or so. Each book ends with an excerpt from the next volume, a preview clearly designed to encourage further reading of the series. And not just reading, either: ownership. These previews are always preceded by a page that urges readers, "Add more Goosebumps to your collection." Each volume has a number prominently displayed on its spine, and the volumes all share the same graphic design, with different titles in the same fonts and different pictures in the same boxes. Like all collectibles, each book looks similar enough to the others to be part of what is clearly a set, but is different enough to make the set incomplete without it.

In *Attack of the Mutant*, Goosebumps #25, the main character, a comic book collector, has a conversation with a girl who collects a different and to his mind inferior kind of comics, and who tells him, "I don't want to sell them. And I don't care what they're worth. I just like to read them" (20). He scornfully replies, "Then you're not a real collector." The collectability and popularity of the Goosebumps series reflects the degree to which children already share or are willing to learn similar attitudes about the gratification of ownership. It's interesting, then, that the girl who wanted only to collect for the pleasure of the reading turns out not to be a human child at all, but a villainous alien, the mutant of the title in disguise. It is inhuman, it seems, not to want to have things—and even, perhaps, essentially human to define one's being in terms of what one owns.

Goosebumps signify membership in the community of acceptable, non-alien children. A number of parents have told me that their children ask for Goosebumps even if they don't particularly enjoy reading them. Just to own them gives one status in the culture of the playground, and not owning any or not having read any marginalizes children within that culture. To have Goosebumps is to be acceptably "normal."

Nor does it hurt that so many adults have expressed dismay about the books and still tend to consider them trash. Their value in the culture of childhood increases exactly in relation to the amount of adult concern and disapproval. The more adult anxiety, the more fun it is—and the more important it is in maintaining your communal status—to read them.³

Young children defy their parents and teachers by reading Goosebumps just as older children (and adults) defy authority by listening to rock music. Both the Goosebumps and the

music are the products of highly profitable economic ventures, their success orchestrated by business interests that represent the exact opposite of rebellion against mainstream practices and values. And both Goosebumps and rock encourage rebellion only in order to coopt and absorb it. For one thing, rebelliousness has been deflected into the consumption of consumer products and sustains the economy; the anarchic and aberrant has come to uphold the very forces of normalcy it purports to oppose. For another, if reading the books or listening to the music is itself an act of rebellion, then rebelliousness is expressed and satisfied in the mere acts of reading and listening. The power structure is safe from any actual efforts to change it.

The particular form of rebellion against adult assumptions that Goosebumps represent emerges from the fact that they are horror stories. They are supposed to be terrifying. Adults try to arrange the lives of children so that they will be safe from fear; but in the culture of the schoolyard, to acknowledge fear is to be defined as a weakling, and to test one's fearlessness an ongoing activity. Not surprisingly, then, the marketing of Goosebumps often implies that the books offer such a test. The teaser on the cover of *One Day in Horrorland*, #16, does so explicitly; it says, "Enter if you dare. . . ."

All of this suggests that Goosebumps encourage the most widely held values of contemporary consumer culture. Their marketing supports self-indulgence and the importance of gratifying desire; the belief that adult concerns are authoritarian and the encouragement of rebellion against them; the importance of status with other children, and the lack of importance of pleasing or agreeing with conventional adults and with conventional adult ideas about behavior or morality or literary excellence; the importance of ownership in defining self-worth and one's worth in the eyes of others; and the superiority of tough-minded fearlessness over a theoretically cowardly refusal to test oneself in the face of a loathsome danger.

But these are exactly the values that parents and teachers often work to discourage children from sharing. Parental and educational discourse both with children and about them—and also, the kinds of books for children that adults most often recommend—tend to privilege the opposite viewpoints. The books that get starred reviews in library or education journals and win important prizes praise moderation rather than indulgence; concern for others rather than self-gratification; charity and self-sacrifice rather than ownership and self-aggrandizement; thoughtfulness rather than willfulness; responsible, safe behavior rather than foolhardy defiance of danger. In allowing and encouraging children to indulge in the opposite of what we would like to consider admirable and acceptable, Goosebumps once more make that which is aberrant and monstrously self-indulgent acceptable—merely normal.

The Normal World in Goosebumps: The Ordinary as Monstrous

The world the Goosebumps books depict as normal—the place where the characters live as it is before the monstrous aberration appears within it—confirms the values engaged by their marketing. The main characters are "normal" to a degree that makes them decidedly unconvincing as possibly existing human beings.

They are sometimes male, sometimes female (and gender doesn't seem to be much of an issue because these characters tend to share personality traits whatever their sex); but they are always twelve. They usually describe themselves as being more or less average in appearance, and their clothing represents fairly current mainstream young adolescent fashion: baseball caps, Doc Martens, jeans, and T-shirts.

The tastes and interests of Stine's protagonists are similarly mainstream. Unless they have a specific hobby, such as playing the piano (*Piano Lessons Can Be Murder*, #13) or worm-collecting (*Go Eat Worms!* #21), that is required by the plot of the book, they tend to do only what we usually assume typical children normally do: they go to school, hang around with each other, watch television. While the plots sometimes separate these children from their parents, they almost always live in two-parent families. Grandparents or other relatives are rarely present. The protagonists often have younger siblings and occasionally older ones—and if they do, they constantly squabble with them. They usually have one or two close friends, but are neither especially popular nor especially unpopular.

The families of these children aren't rich, but they enjoy enough material comfort not to need to comment on it. There's a similar lack of detail about the settings, but they usually sound like suburbs or small towns. While some books take place during farm or beach vacations, the children never actually live on farms or in urban apartments. Nor do they often live in clearly definable areas with distinctive geographical features or specific regional accents. There's also almost no mention of race or ethnicity unless the plot demands it—as it does, for instance, in two books about mummies, which specify their protagonists' Egyptian background. These children seem to be white de-ethnicized mid-Americans, devoid of any consciousness of a specific cultural heritage. And they never express any sort of interest in sex or gangs or drugs.

For all the tank tops and Doc Martens, the world the books describe sounds more like a nostalgic portrait of a sitcom America of the fifties than a representation of today. In light of the focus on multiculturalism in contemporary pedagogy and children's publishing, the whiteness of Goosebumps is especially noteworthy. But most of the things that usually create problems for children—differences in race or appearance or economic status, family upheaval or religious conflict

or sexual confusion or lack of popularity—simply don't exist in the "normal" world of Goosebumps.

In this way, Goosebumps represent a version of a popular ploy of contemporary commercial culture: to persuade us that "normal" means, not what people normally do or are, but a desirable ideal, what you need to do or be if you want to think of yourself as being normal. For instance, fashion magazines persuade many readers that to be normal is to be much thinner than most women are. Those persuaded of this view will work hard and spend a lot of money to achieve "normalcy."

If child readers accept the idealized fictional world of Goosebumps as an accurate representation of reality—and surely that's the intention, if the readers are to appreciate the ways in which the various horrors diverge from normalcy—then they are learning or confirming a decidedly limited view of what's normal. In Goosebumps, furthermore, this identifiable norm is not just an empty space. The protagonists share not only external circumstances but a character. They tend, in fact, to display all of the characteristics that I earlier suggested the marketing of the books encourages. Consider some typical passages:

She's jealous, Lindy realized. Kris sees that the kids really like Slappy [a ventriloquist's dummy] and that I'm getting all the attention. And she's totally jealous.

I'm *definitely* keeping Slappy! Lindy told herself, secretly pleased at her little triumph. (*Night of the Living Dummy* #7, 15)

Andy pushed past him and took the can [of Monster Blood] from Evan's hand. "Oooh, I want one, too," she said, turning the can around in her hand.

"There's only one," Evan told her.

"You sure?" She began searching the shelves. . . .

"I need one, too," Andy said to Evan.

"Sorry," Evan replied, taking the can back. "I saw it first."

"I'll buy it from you," Andy said. (*Monster Blood* #3, 33)

"Hey, Eddie—was it *you* who put that dumb snake in my lunch?"

"Of course not," I exclaimed. I kicked the grass with my sneaker. . . .

"I thought maybe it was you," Courtney said, tossing her hair behind her shoulder. "I thought maybe you were trying to pay me back. You know. For the green snake thing."

"No way," I muttered. "No way, Courtney." . . .

Finally, Courtney raised her feet to the pedals and rode off down the street.

"We've got to find a way to scare her," I said through clenched teeth as soon as she had ridden out of sight. "We've just got to!" (*You Can't Scare Me!* #15, 33-34)

These scenes describe typical Goosebumps children. They are decidedly egocentric. They rarely report any feelings about others except insofar as those others' actions affect themselves. They are very conscious of the power of ownership. They often express envy over someone else's possessions or enjoy the envy created in others by their own possessions. They are also, and most notably, incredibly competitive. They compete for parental attention and about who will have the best science fair display and just about anything else. And in all of these competitions they are less interested in what they might win than in the mere fact that they have won. But most significantly, these children compete to see whether they can scare each other. These books focus almost obsessively on the effort of children to frighten other children and on the importance of not being frightened.

All of this material is presented without question or comment, as normal—as what children usually are, and as what readers are invited to identify with and imagine themselves to be. Nor, as we might expect from our reading of more critically acclaimed children's fiction about similarly hard-nosed, self-involved, and self-trusting children, do these children find their values particularly questioned by the events of the plot. In "Most Intriguing: R. L. Stine," *People* quotes Stine as saying, "I have no crying, no hugging, and the kids never learn anything about themselves." And that's true—his children lack both the emotional vulnerability implied by crying and the concern for and interaction with others implied by hugging; and they never change enough to learn anything about themselves.

Anything new, that is. The children's books that adults tend to admire most often encourage identification with characters as an invitation for readers to change as the characters do and learn to be better—to grow up. Consider just about any Newbery Medal winner. Goosebumps apparently encourage identification to reinforce the idea that no change is necessary. Once more, Goosebumps seem to be in the act of confirming values that do perhaps govern mainstream culture and that are of great value to commerce: egoists and competitors are excellent consumers.

But as I suggested earlier, it's exactly values like these that adults often work hard to dissuade children of, to make seem aberrant and monstrous. In allowing these monstrosities without comment, Goosebumps once more work to make the theoretically aberrant normal.

The Horror: The Monstrous as Ordinary

Into this world comes a more obvious horror. Each book in the series describes how a child confronts something obviously and undeniably monstrous. Being monstrous, the

monsters of horror are by definition unnatural, abnormal. As Noël Carroll suggests in his *Philosophy of Horror*, “the monsters of horror . . . breach the norms of ontological propriety presumed by the positive human characters in the story. . . . The monster is an extraordinary character in our ordinary world” (16). It isn’t much of a stretch to conclude that monsters represent that which our conceptions of normalcy exclude or deny—what we see not only as aberrant or deformed, but as frighteningly so, come to life and interfering with normalcy. Most theoretical considerations of the meaning of horror focus on the significance of that disruption.

From a psychoanalytical point of view, horror represents a return of the repressed. The psychoanalyst Ernest Jones once suggested that the imagery of horror is repulsive but entertaining because it manifests forbidden or repressed wishes. The disgust we feel for the monsters of horror masks a desire for that which we are not supposed to desire—hence the thrill of engaging the disgust and the pleasure we get from it. Speaking of fantasy in general, Rosemary Jackson offers a similar dynamic, but puts it in the context of cultural forces:

fantasy characteristically attempts to compensate for a lack resulting from cultural constraints: it is a literature of desire, which seeks that which is experienced as absence and loss. . . . The fantastic traces the unsaid and the unseen of culture: that which has been silenced, made invisible, covered over and made “absent.” (3, 5)

In this light, it is revealing that something like horror fiction first appeared in the late eighteenth century; in a time when Enlightenment thinking celebrated the triumph of reason and order, the “Gothic” novels of writers such as Horace Walpole and Ann Radcliffe explored the disordered emotions and irrational possibilities that the culture generally worked to suppress as primitive or counterproductive.

Seen from these points of view, all fantasy is subversive; in her subtitle, Jackson calls it “the literature of subversion.” Horror, the kind of fantasy that focuses on monstrosity, ought then to subvert readers’ conceptions of monstrosity. If what passes as normalcy in Goosebumps is frighteningly combative and self-seeking, then the monsters might well represent something readers might find more comforting—a way of moving beyond the egocentric values of consumer culture. The monster might in fact be a means of expressing subversive and desirable alternatives.

If they are alternatives, though, that doesn’t necessarily make them subversive. According to Jackson,

In expressing desire, fantasy can operate in two ways. . . . it can *tell of*, manifest or show desire (expression in the sense of portrayal, representation, manifestation, linguistic utterance, mention, description), or it can *expel* desire, when this desire

is a disturbing element which threatens cultural order and continuity (expression in the sense of pressing out, squeezing, expulsion, getting rid of something by force). In many cases fantastic literature fulfils both functions at once, for desire can be “expelled” by having been told of and thus vicariously experienced by author and reader. (3-4)

Stephen King, the most successful contemporary writer of horror fiction for adults, offers a theory of fantasy that focuses on this kind of expelling. According to King,

horror fiction is really as Republican as a banker in a three-piece suit. The story is always the same in terms of development. There’s an incursion into taboo lands, there’s a place where you shouldn’t go, but you do, the same way that your mother would tell you that the freak tent is a place you shouldn’t go, but you do. And the same thing happens inside: you look at the skeleton man or Mr. Electrical or whoever it happens to be. And when you come out, well, you say, “Hey, I’m not so bad. I’m all right. A lot better than I thought.” It has that effect of reconfirming values, of reconfirming self-image and our good feelings about ourselves. . . . the creator of horror is above all an agent of the norm. (Qtd. in Carroll, 199)

From this point of view, the whole point of horror is that it comes to an end. The monstrous is evoked only in order to be expelled.

King’s own novels confirm his theory; in the ones I’ve read, normalcy always returns at the end. Furthermore, ordinary people, often children, have a hand in making that happen: the normal actively works to conquer and expel the monstrous.⁴ That’s a pattern anyone familiar with children’s literature will recognize: fiction for children often ends with an expulsion of danger and a return to normalcy. But Goosebumps books don’t necessarily follow that pattern.

Sometimes the horror just disappears, or is destroyed quite by accident. In *Night of the Living Dummy*, #7, for instance, one of the evil ventriloquist dummies that have begun to exert control over the girls operating them is suddenly and accidentally run over by a steam roller; and in *Go Eat Worms!*, a giant papier-mâché bird just happens accidentally to scare away a threatening giant worm. Sometimes the children do something to defeat the monster—figure out a defense, as in *The Scarecrow Walks at Midnight*, #20. Sometimes, in fact, they don’t defeat it—it gets them, as at the end of *Be Careful What You Wish For*, #12, where the main character turns into a bird. Sometimes, the children become the thing they fear: they turn into monsters themselves, a werewolf (*The Werewolf of Fever Swamp*, #14) or an alien (*The Girl Who Cried Monster*, #8) or a dog (*My Hairiest Adventure*,

#26). And sometimes one horror disappears—perhaps defeated by a child—only to be replaced at the end by another (*Ghost Beach*, #22). If Goosebumps are in the business of expelling subversive ideas, they are going about it in strange ways.

Indeed, and paradoxically, King's adult novels read like fairly straightforward and highly formulaic wish-fulfillment fantasies, in which unheroically ordinary underdogs triumph over grossly perverse monsters, clearly represented as evil and in need of being expelled, in order to regain (and celebrate) the norm; whereas the theoretically simpler Goosebumps represent a much more unsettled and more complex state of affairs, one in which underdogs sometimes appear to lose and in which the monstrous is not always in fact expelled. Are Goosebumps then actually subversive of normalcy in ways that King's own novels are not?

I can begin to answer that question by returning to the context in which horror arises: normalcy as Stine represents it. The world of Goosebumps is already filled with questions of fear and horror and monstrosity even before actual monsters enter it. As I suggested earlier, a majority of the characters are practical jokers, busily engaged with their friends or siblings in a game of scaring and being scared. And as Stine continually makes clear as he describes these competitions, he or she who scares best wins power—is recognized and admired as a victor by the victims and by others. As a result, the protagonists often wish that they could scare the wits out of someone who is always scaring them, or who gets at them in some other way. In this context of feigned monstrosity, the actual monster is often indistinguishable from and at first confused with the jokes. The monster's power seems less an aberration from normative values than a hyperbolic expression of them.

That monstrosity might be merely normal seems to be confirmed especially in those Goosebumps in which child protagonists actually become monsters themselves. Having tried to win power over their friends by pretending to be monstrous, and having then had to acknowledge (merely by being frightened) the fearful power of real monstrosity, these children finally become as scary as the original monsters that scared them—frightening to others and, therefore, triumphantly powerful. These books then offer a double vision of the monstrous. It is both what one fears (because it is frightening to oneself) and what one must learn to desire (because it is frightening to others). The characters in these books often actually express this double attitude; readers must always experience it in order to enjoy fully the pleasure the novels offer.

Carroll suggests that horror fiction engages its audiences by putting readers and viewers in the position of characters to whom horrific things happen so that "the emotional reactions of characters . . . provide a set of instructions, or rather, examples about the way in which the audience is to respond" (17). If Carroll is right, and if a child reader accepts the

invitation to identify with a protagonist early in these novels, then the instructions that Stine gives have unsettling implications. These books offer child readers a variation on Darwinism, based on the survival of the scariest: in a world where fear is power, you must learn to be the most frightening of all.

That dynamic seems to account also for another group of Goosebumps books in which the protagonist is actually defeated by the monster. Here, horror triumphs. We have no choice but to feel tricked or unhappy and dissatisfied, or else to withdraw our identification from the protagonist and view the protagonist's defeat as a happy ending, thus again confirming the power of horror.

In books in which the child *does* defeat the scary thing, furthermore, the victory tends to involve doing something scary. In *Stay Out of the Basement*, #2, for instance, a child must wield an axe to cut down a mutated plant that looks like and might actually *be* her own father. This axe-wielding potential father-murderer is easily as frightening as the horror she attacks. Indeed, she must be willing to be frighteningly single-minded in order to win. Thus, scariness triumphs again—once more confirming the power of horror.

In some other books, finally, the horror ceases without any action being required on the part of the protagonist. It just ends, or an accident does it in. This ending also confirms the power of horror. Its essence is its anarchic ability to upset norms, defy expectations. Horror comes of its own will and goes of its own will. Mere normal mortals do not, in fact, have any power over it.

Thus, these different sorts of endings share similar implications. In a world of fear, being monstrously frightening is not only normal but necessary. Furthermore, whichever one of these things happens in any particular book also seems to be entirely a matter of random choice. I could easily imagine each of them actually happening in each of the books, had Stine chosen that day to make that happen. And this sense confirms a peculiar randomness that is one of the most distinctive qualities of the series.

The most typical characteristic of series fiction is its adherence to formula. It offers readers pleasure by following a common pattern of events and by always focusing on the same kinds of characters, events, and interests. But for all the stereotypical normalcy of their characters and settings, Goosebumps are oddly unformulaic in plot. While the plots always involve some child being scared by something, they develop in apparently random ways, without adherence to a specific sequence or pattern. It often seems at the end of a chapter that something truly horrific has happened—and then, at the beginning of the next chapter, it turns out just to be some ordinary object lying on the floor that looked like a monster. But only sometimes. The next time around it actually does turn out to have been a monster. Or maybe it doesn't. Sometimes a scary event turns out to have been a dream. Or sometimes it doesn't. A reader can never really know which.

And that seems to be the point. Fear emerges when the unexpected happens; in the context of reading a horror story, the unexpected sometimes happens when the unexpected *doesn't* happen. If it didn't, we would learn to expect it and cease to be frightened by it. In this context, the apparent randomness of Stine's endings merely confirms the apparent randomness of earlier events. No matter how any one of the books ends, the series as a whole suggests that horror never stops, that normal order is never firmly established. This is a random world we live in, and it continues always to be so.

Even the provenance of horror—what accounts for its existence—is random. Stine sometimes offers scientific explanations for monstrous events or creatures (as in *Stay Out of the Basement* or in *Piano Lessons Can Be Murder*), sometimes supernatural ones such as witchcraft (*Monster Blood*, #3) or ghosts (*Welcome to Dead House*, #1), and sometimes none at all. There is no cohesive system of knowledge or faith or ethics that has the power to contain and control the randomness of reality. Once again, the disruptive anarchy of horror is less a disruption of normalcy than an exaggerated expression of it.

In King's novels, the opposite is true: horror represents the opposite of normalcy. Indeed, it represents an opposition to normalcy. King often insists that his monsters derive their power from the willingness of some of his characters to give in to their own antisocial tendencies, to indulge in excessive violence or illicit lust or uncontrolled anger.⁵ Not surprisingly, then, the power to dissipate the disruptive monstrosity most often comes from the ability of other characters to resist antisocial tendencies and to act upon the values that we like to believe bind normal families and communities together: love, optimism about the power of humans to be good, self-sacrifice, concern for the needs of others.

Stine's world is neither so innocent nor so meaningful. Since horror doesn't necessarily represent anything evil or antisocial, or emerge because people have fallen away from an ideal, it can appear at any time for no reason whatsoever. And while some kinds of faith or action can sometimes defeat a specific manifestation of horror, sometimes they can't. In such a world, being innocent, or trusting ideals of love or concern for others, or having hope or optimism are not particularly wise choices. It's no wonder that Stine's children manifest none of these values. Since how you act or what your ethics are has little to do with whether or not horror happens to you, your only wise choice is to be prepared for anything by fearing nothing, by being fearsome, by being the scariest monster in a monstrously anarchic world. In their egocentric self-seeking desire to be frightening, Stine's children define the best response to horror in a horrific world. Once more, horror is merely the way things normally are.

Why Monsters?

If Stine's monsters merely confirm the monstrosity of what he depicts as normal reality—what, indeed, he appears to

believe *is* normal and perfectly acceptable reality — we might ask why he bothers to write horror fiction at all. If the world is itself already horrific, what can possibly be gained by introducing actual monsters into it? Isn't it scary enough already? The answer, I think, is that it's *too* scary. According to one of Stine's characters, in fact, "People need to create monsters. . . . It helps us to believe that the real world isn't quite as scary" (*You Can't Scare Me*, #95).

As I hope I've shown, the dynamics of Goosebumps replicate the desirability of exactly the behavior that is taken for granted by their protagonists and encouraged by their marketing: be egocentric, be fearless, be a winner. These might well be "normal," even desirable, characteristics in the market-oriented consumer society contemporary children are growing up in. But they are not the values the adult establishment usually works to encourage in children. Nor, as the popularity of King's novels with adults makes clear, are they the values many North Americans hold as ideals, claim allegiance to, and like to imagine operating in our lives—or in the lives of children. Stine's books reveal a tension between what we claim to believe (and would like children to believe) and the values many of us actually act on (and often unwittingly encourage children to act on).

If that's the case, Goosebumps represent a particularly interesting case of the expression of what Jackson calls "the unseen and unsaid of culture": not, as Jackson implies, that which has been declared disorderly or illegal or forbidden, but that which has been declared disorderly or illegal or forbidden to notice or to acknowledge or to celebrate. As I read them, Goosebumps do in fact notice, acknowledge, and celebrate the forbidden, through the clever stratagem of presenting it, not only as fantasy, but also as monstrous and horrific—and then celebrating the power of the monstrous and the horrific so that it comes to seem both fearful and desirable, both the most antisocial evil and the ultimate social good. According to Fredric Jameson, "the aesthetic act is itself ideological, and the production of aesthetic or narrative form is to be seen as an ideological act in its own right, with the function of inventing imaginary or formal 'solutions' to unresolvable social contradictions" (79). The Goosebumps books represent such a solution.

The problem being solved is this: in an atmosphere of declared allegiance to principles of charity and societal regulation, we must at least pay lip service to the principle that the kind of fearless and frightening egocentric competitiveness that might increase one's personal capital in a world of fear is negative behavior—horrific, in fact. And we have a particular obligation to teach children our declared ideals. On the other hand, and though I'm sure most adults wouldn't acknowledge it, I'm convinced that many of us also want children to know exactly how very theoretical these ideals are and how little they do or should govern their actual behavior. Even if we don't believe or aren't aware that our adherence to the ideals is

theoretical, the push to make adherence to them merely theoretical is certainly a fact of mainstream ideology. In order for that which has power to maintain itself in our consumer culture, children must grow up to be good consumers, that is, self-gratifying competitors with the will to win enough money and the power to indulge themselves at will—people whose actual commitment to self-sacrifice or concern for others is minimal.

As I've described them, Goosebumps solve this "unresolvable social contradiction" in a number of ways. First, they present egocentric behavior, and particularly the competition to frighten others, as an inevitable given in the behavior of the "normal" children they invite readers to identify with. Furthermore, the books are silent about the moral or ethical implications of this behavior. It is simply the way things are, and presumably the only way things can be; as Stine says, he doesn't try to change his readers. Then, and most significantly, after establishing this norm of conduct and the wish to be frightening as a typical goal, the books represent the theoretically antisocial as monstrous, a move that seems to separate the typical and therefore non-monstrous child protagonists from what they have desired and to make its supposedly antisocial danger clear. But the separation also makes the monstrous fantastic, a clear intrusion of the imaginary into normal reality that divests it of its relevance as a real concern in terms of a reader's own desire or behaviors. If the monstrous is, after all, only a fantasy, it is not something to really be concerned about in one's own life. Having thus been divested of dangerous relevance, the fearful power of the Goosebumps monsters can be enjoyed without any conscious awareness of the implications of their various triumphs. The readers who respond as Goosebumps invite them to respond both desire that which is theoretically monstrous and fearful—they value fear—and are not aware of that desire.

In other words, for these readers, the monstrous has become normal. The monstrous has become allowable. Goosebumps are merely ordinary.

Reading Something

Should adults approve of children reading Goosebumps, "as long as they're reading something"? The answer to that question depends on the degree to which the adults in question themselves accept what Goosebumps invite young readers to believe and to become. Do we share these values ourselves? And do we want young readers to share them also?

Whether we do or not, I think it's safe to postulate that, for most child readers, Goosebumps are more likely to confirm and to amplify their already existing sense of themselves and the world than to challenge them. That seems likely simply because of the astonishing popularity of the series. Best-selling fiction, almost by definition, is that which tells readers what they like to hear, what they know already.⁶ If Goosebumps

follow the norms of best-selling fiction, then, they are more likely to affirm their readers' existing assumptions or wish-fulfillment fantasies than they are to challenge them or to offer new or different ideas. The books are likely to be inherently conservative and to work to confirm attitudes that maintain the status quo. They are likely to encourage readers to believe that what they already know about themselves and their world is the complete and only truth.

And they do exactly that. The values of Goosebumps are the most common values of the playground (at least once adult eyes are turned). They are also, I suspect, the values adults in contemporary North America most usually have to cope with and act by in their daily lives, despite hypocritical claims to tolerance and concern for others. And perhaps just as significantly, they are the values represented in popular television shows and movies and toys directed at audiences of children. By the time most North American children get around to reading Goosebumps, they will have already spent a lifetime immersed in cartoons and commercials and tie-in toy sets that mirror the monstrous normalcy of the world of Goosebumps. They will know the place already and feel quite comfortable in it.

If the popularity of Goosebumps distresses us, then, it should not be because they represent an aberrant outbreak of the monstrous in the otherwise benevolent world of children's culture. Their immense popularity with children should tell us how very ordinary this particular form of the monstrous already is to them; and that information ought to lead us to want to help children develop strategies that will allow them to become aware of the monstrousness and, I hope, to defend themselves against it. Yes, children should be reading Goosebumps—but with an active critical awareness that prevents the world they describe from seeming merely ordinary and merely the ways things always and inevitably are.

NOTES

¹I'm basing these observations on presentations on Goosebumps that I've made in a variety of forums, attended by parents, teachers, and librarians, and also on surveys done by students in various of my courses exploring the attitudes of a wide variety of adults toward the series.

²In a May 1994 listing of "Children's Best Sellers," *The New York Times Book Review* reported that "the most popular books on these lists are, overwhelmingly, the new Goosebumps' series. . . . Sales for the Goosebumps' series are nearly equal to the total sales of all the other 15 ranked series combined." A year later, at one point during the fall of 1995, according to a *People* magazine article naming Stine one of the most intriguing people of the year, *The Headless Ghost*, Goosebumps #37, was the best-selling book in *all* categories. In October 1995, in fact, Marc Silver suggested that "the 38 paperback volumes might be literature's most popular series, selling more than 1 million copies a month." As I write in the summer of 1997, the popularity of Goosebumps has finally begun to wane a little, after four years of unprecedented success and huge sales.

³The same marketing ploy that successfully launched Goosebumps is represented in more extreme fashion in the Barforama books, launched during the summer of 1996. The success of the series, which consists of theoretically hilarious stories about children vomiting and excreting and otherwise eliminating various forms of bodily waste, depends exactly on the degree to which adults express disgust with it and with children's enjoyment of it.

⁴I'm thinking particularly of *It*. But unheroic humans defeat horrific forces in almost all of King's novels.

⁵The willingness of "typical" Americans to give in to various of the seven deadly sins allows fantastic monstrosity to enter an otherwise non-fantastic world in, to name a few, *Cujo*, *The Shining*, *It*, and *Needful Things*.

⁶In discussing his reading of such literature, John Cawelti suggests that "its purpose is not to make me confront motives and experiences in myself that I might prefer to ignore, but to take me out of myself by confirming an idealized self-image" (18). Paradoxically, here, being "taken out" of oneself is a matter of not having to consider the uglier implications of being oneself as one already is—and therefore, of not actually being taken anywhere, of remaining exactly where one is already. This confirms, curiously, Stine's observation that his readers "never learn anything about themselves."

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Perry Nodelman's latest novel for young adults, Behaving Bradley, will be published in the U.S. and Canada by Simon and Schuster in Spring 1998. It offers a comic look at "normal" life in a contemporary high school.

